

A comparative study of kinematic and kinetic analysis of gait in patients with non-specific low back pain versus healthy controls

Mohammad Taghi KARIMI¹, Maryam Hasan ZAHRAEE², Mahmood BAHRAMIZADEH^{3*}
Hanieh KHALILIYAN⁴, Majid ANSARI⁵, Farhad GHAFARI⁶, Arash SHARAFATVAZIRI⁷

Cite this paper as: Karimi MT, Zahraee MH, Bahramizadeh M, Khaliliyan H, Ansari M, Ghaffari F, Sharafatvaziri A. A comparative study of kinematic and kinetic analysis of gait in patients with non-specific low back pain versus healthy controls. Adv Med Psychol Public Health. 2025;2(2):107-116. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13196403

¹Department of Orthotics and Prosthetics, School of Rehabilitation Sciences, Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Shiraz, Iran. E-mail: mohammad.karimi.bioengineering@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0001-6162-8131

²Musculoskeletal Research Center, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Isfahan, Iran. E-mail: m1988z@yahoo.com ORCID: 0009-0005-0420-9041

³Department of Orthotics and Prosthetics, University of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Sciences, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: mbzgoandp@gmail.com; ma.bahramizadeh@uswr.ac.ir ORCID: 0000-0003-4719-938x

⁴Department of Orthotics and Prosthetics, School of Rehabilitation Sciences, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Isfahan, Iran. E-mail: haniehkhaliliyan@yahoo.com ORCID: 0000-0002-6400-5826

⁵Rehabilitation Medicine, Erfan Hospital, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: majid.ansari@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0000-4572-1141

⁶Khatam-Alanbia hospital, Orthopedic Department, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: Farhadb75@yahoo.com ORCID: 0009-0006-7412-0357

⁷Center for Orthopedic Trans-Disciplinary Applied Research, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran. Email: arash.sharafatvaziri@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-4139-0071

*Correspondence

Abstract

Introduction: Low back pain (LBP) is a common health and socioeconomic problem, especially the chronic one. It may affect the gait pattern of the patients. The aim of this study was to evaluate the motions of pelvis, trunk and legs in the subjects with non-specific chronic low back pain (NCLBP).

Method: This was an cross sectional study in which 40 subjects including 20 normal subjects and 20 NCLBP patients were recruited. The force applied on the leg, the range of motion of trunk, pelvic, lower extremity, the moments applied to the joints and spatiotemporal gait parameters were selected for this study.

Results: The mean values of walking speed of normal subjects and NCLBP patients were 0.89 ± 0.13 and 0.95 ± 0.09 m/s, respectively ($p=0.24$). The mean value of the second peak of ground reaction force of normal and NCLBP subjects was 1.13 ± 0.045 and 1.106 ± 0.035 N/WB, respectively ($p=0.038$).

Conclusion: There was a significant difference between the kinematics of the hip joints in the normal and NCLBP subjects. The interesting point of the current study was that those with NCLBP had a decrease in hip, knee, and ankle joint moments, maybe due to muscular weakness.

Take-home message: This study found that while spatiotemporal gait parameters and joint range of motion did not significantly differ, NCLBP patients exhibited reduced joint moments, suggesting muscular weakness. Strengthening exercises for hip, knee extensors, and ankle plantar flexors are recommended to improve gait function in NCLBP patients.

Keywords: Gait; ground reaction force; moment; non-specific chronic low back pain; kinematic.

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain (LBP) is one of the most prevalent musculoskeletal conditions and a relevant health problem globally [1]. Although the lifetime prevalence of LBP experiencing an acute phase is 60-80% [2], 5% of patients will develop sub-acute and chronic LBP (CLBP)[2,3]. Most LBP (especially CLBP) are non-specific, containing conditions with no clear pathological cause. The most important symptoms of non-specific LBP (NLBP) are pain and disability [4], primarily occupational disability [5]. One area that has received attention in this respect is the effect of LBP on gait parameters [6], the most common form of human locomotion. Moreover, gait analysis is an essential aspect of assessment in the clinical evaluation of gait disturbances and rehabilitation [7].

Based on the research done by Lamothe et al., those with LBP showed longer stance duration and shorter step lengths than healthy subjects [8,9]. They concluded that reduced stride length might be a mechanism to reduce and avoid pain (rigid structure). Another study found that LBP subjects' pattern and range of lumbar and pelvic motions are the same as normal subjects [8]. Vogt et al. showed that in NLBP, the amplitude of pelvic motions was the same as in normal-matched subjects, although it has a high degree of variability [10]. Moreover, they showed that NLBP subjects walked with larger pelvic rotation to maintain their stride length. Furthermore, another study showed that, due to disc herniation, those with LBP have reduced relative phase between pelvic and thoracic horizontal, especially in larger steps [11]. The motions of most body segments (pelvic trunk) are three-dimensional. In LBP subjects, the variability of sagittal plane motions (flexion-extension) is less than normal; however, there seems to be no difference between the motions of the frontal plane. The most commonly reported parameter regarding the gait of the subjects with LBP is the range of motion. The results of the studies regarding this parameter are conflicting [12]. Vogt et al. concluded that the difference between normal and those with LBP is statistically significant [10,13]. In contrast, MacRae et al. observed no differences between normal and the patients with NCLBP for spatiotemporal parameters, maximum, minimum, and total ranges of hip movement, and flexor and extensor moments [14]. The decrease in hip joint moment may be due to a reduction in ground reaction forces applied on the leg (a compensatory mechanism employed by the subjects to decrease pain) [15]. Alteration in proprioception in the subjects with NCLBP is another reason for a change in the hip and pelvis kinematics [16].

Although the moments produced by muscles are other important parameters evaluated in some research studies [17-19], no study focused on this parameter in three dimensions in LBP subjects. Furthermore, there is insufficient evidence in the literature on the kinematic evaluation of lower limb joints, pelvis, and trunk in LBP subjects. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the pelvis, trunk, and legs' motions in the NCLBP subjects. Moreover, the aim was to find the moments applied to the leg in this group of subjects. The main hypothesis associated with this study was that there was no difference between LBP and normal subjects regarding kinetic and kinematic parameters.

METHODS

Study design

This cross-sectional study involved 20 normal individuals and 20 patients with non-specific chronic low back pain (NCLBP). The normal subjects were matched with the patients based on age and height.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria for participation in this study are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria used for the patients who participated in the study.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female • Age: 25- 55 years • Pain group: • History of NSCLBP ≥ 6 months duration • Without peripheral pain referral • Pain in the area from T12 to gluteal folds • Moderate ongoing LBP • Average daily pain level – VAS > 2/10 • Experienced most days of the week • Mechanically induced localized LBP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific diagnosis associated with LBP such as spondylolisthesis, disc prolapse, inflammatory disorders • Presence of other conditions affecting the spine, including neurological or metastatic disease • Any neurological deficit Any surgery involving the lumbar spine • Any diagnosed pelvic or abdominal pain disorder in the last 12 months • Pregnancy or less than six months post-partum • Any lower limb surgery in the last two years • Current lower limb injury • An inability to understand written or spoken Persian

Control group

- No history of spinal pain or musculoskeletal disorders
- No previous diagnosis or treatment for low back pain
- No presence of any condition affecting the spine, including neurological or metastatic diseases
- No history of any surgical procedures involving the lumbar spine
- No diagnosed pelvic or abdominal pain disorders in the last 12 months
- No history of lower limb surgeries in the last 2 years
- No current lower limb injuries
- Ability to understand and follow written and spoken Persian instructions

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Shiraz University of Medical Sciences (Ethics number: IR.SUMS.REHAB.REC.1399.034). Prior to participation, all subjects were fully informed about the study procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Each subject provided written informed consent in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The confidentiality of the participants was maintained throughout the study. This study adhered to the guidelines provided by the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) for observational studies.

Study procedure

The selected parameters for this study included the force applied to the leg, the range of motion of the trunk, pelvis, and lower extremities, the moments applied to the joints, and spatiotemporal gait parameters. To trace the subjects' movements, a motion analysis system with seven high-speed cameras (Qualysis system from Switzerland) was used.

A Kistler force plate was employed to determine the force applied to the leg. Data collection was managed using Tract Manager software by Qualysis Company, and Visual 3D software (C-Motion Company) was used for anatomical reconstruction and calculation of joint angles during walking. Figure 1 shows the markers attached to body landmarks in this study.

Figure 1. The configuration of markers attached to the body in this study.

Instrumentation and data collection

Markers were attached to both sides of the body at specific anatomical landmarks, including the iliac crest, anterior and posterior superior iliac spine, greater trochanter, knee epicondyles, malleolus, heel, metatarsal heads, and acromioclavicular joints. Extensible Velcro straps with marker clusters were placed on the right and left shank, thigh, and trunk.

Data processing and analysis

Subjects were asked to walk along a level surface to collect five successful trials. Data were collected at a frequency of 120 Hz and filtered using a Butterworth low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 10 Hz. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normal distribution of all parameters. A two-sample t-test was used for normally distributed parameters to compare the differences between normal and NCLBP subjects, with significance set at $\alpha=0.05$.

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 26). Descriptive statistics (mean \pm SD) were calculated for each parameter. Independent t-tests were conducted to compare the gait parameters between the normal and NCLBP groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study compared the characteristics and gait parameters between subjects with non-specific chronic low back pain (NCLBP) and normal subjects. Detailed statistical analyses assessed differences in spatiotemporal gait parameters, joint kinematics, and moments applied to the hip, knee, and ankle joints. Table 2 shows the characteristics of both groups.

Table 2. The characteristics of NCLBP and normal subjects participated in the study.

Parameter	Groups	
	NCLBP* (n = 20)	Normal (n = 20)
Age (y)	41.56 ± 9.57**	40.18 ± 8.55
Height (cm)	158.81 ± 5.56	158.18 ± 5.74
Mass (kg)	61.68 ± 8.88	60.25 ± 6.38
Sex	Female	Female

Note: * Non-specific Low Back Pain ** Values are mean ± SD

Table 3 shows the mean value of spatiotemporal gait parameters for individuals with normal gait and those with NCLBP. As seen in this table, the walking speed of NCLBP subjects differed from that of normal subjects, but the difference was not significant ($p = 0.24$). The mean value of the second peak of the ground reaction force of normal and NCLBP subjects was 1.13 ± 0.045 and 1.106 ± 0.035 N/BW ($p = 0.038$). The mean values of the other force peaks were the same between normal individuals and those with NCLBP ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3. Spatiotemporal gait parameters.

Parameter	Velocity (m/s)	Cadence (steps/min)	Stride length (cm)
NCLBP	0.89 ± 0.13	67 ± 8	113 ± 9
Normal	0.95 ± 0.09	68 ± 4	117 ± 7
p-value	0.24	0.14	0.17

Table 4. Gait kinematic parameters.

Parameter	Group	NLBP	Normal	P-value
Hip Moments	HMx1	0.29 ± 0.10	0.48 ± 0.24	0.11
	HMx2	0.49 ± 0.20	0.35 ± 0.15	0.53
	HMy	0.84 ± 0.31	0.89 ± 0.31	0.007
	HMz1	0.04 ± 0.02	0.10 ± 0.05	0.04
	HMz2	0.12 ± 0.03	0.06 ± 0.07	0.22
Knee Moments	KMx1	0.22 ± 0.12	0.36 ± 0.16	0.05
	KMx2	0.49 ± 0.12	0.21 ± 0.20	0.08
	KMy	0.37 ± 0.08	0.33 ± 0.09	0.22
	KMz1	0.04 ± 0.08	0.08 ± 0.05	0.19
	KMz2	0.13 ± 0.03	0.06 ± 0.09	0.20
Ankle Moments	AMx1	0.14 ± 0.08	0.07 ± 0.03	0.01
	AMx2	1.44 ± 0.26	1.54 ± 0.10	0.03

Parameter	Group	NLBP	Normal	P-value
	Amy	0.32 ± 0.14	0.22 ± 0.10	0.12
	AMz1	0.02 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.01	0.19
	AMz2	0.13 ± 0.06	0.14 ± 0.05	0.28
Hip Range of Motion	HROMx	39.80 ± 5.04	39.71 ± 1.85	0.33
	HROMy	13.87 ± 2.30	13.40 ± 2.65	0.43
	HROMz	12.38 ± 1.87	12.33 ± 3.46	0.36
Knee Range of Motion	KROMx	66.42 ± 5.90	66.29 ± 5.88	0.23
	KROMy	10.47 ± 4.85	9.69 ± 3.55	0.47
	KROMz	20.36 ± 4.99	18.83 ± 2.98	0.12
Ankle Range of Motion	AROMx	31.85 ± 4.91	34.59 ± 4.55	0.26
	AROMy	23.42 ± 6.03	18.81 ± 4.28	0.14
	AROMz	14.02 ± 8.34	17.42 ± 6.26	0.47
Pelvic Range of Motion	PROMx	6.91 ± 1.50	6.71 ± 1.50	0.38
	PROMy	6.32 ± 2.05	6.75 ± 2.93	0.32
	PROMz	12.65 ± 5.08	14.44 ± 8.00	0.20
Trunk Range of Motion	TROMx	7.07 ± 1.10	12.07 ± 4.54	0.18
	TROMy	7.72 ± 2.16	6.98 ± 1.72	0.48
	TROMz	9.76 ± 2.66	15.40 ± 10.12	0.10

Note: ROM= Range of motion, M=Moments are in 3 dimensions: (ROM) x=Flexion/extension, (ROM) y = Abduction/adduction and (ROM) z=Internal/external rotation, H=Hip, K=Knee, A=Ankle, P=Pelvic, T=Trunk, Mx1= Moment of Extension, Mx2= Moment of Flexion, My= Moment of abduction / Mz1, 2: External/ Internal Rotation moment, respectively.

The flexion moment of the knee joint increased slightly in the subjects with NCLBP. The moments of the ankle joint were the other parameters selected in this study. The mean value of ankle plantar flexion moment decreased significantly in NCLBP subjects (the plantar flexion moment was 1.44 ± 0.26 and 1.54 ± 0.1 Nm/BW for NCLBP and normal subjects, respectively). Figures 2 and 3 show the motions of the pelvic and lumbar spine in both groups of subjects.

Figure 2. Hip joint motion in sagittal (a), Frontal (b), and transverse planes (c) in normal and NLBP subjects.

Figure 3. Pelvic motions in sagittal (a), frontal (b), and transverse planes (c) in a normal and NLBP.

DISCUSSION

LBP is undoubtedly one of the most challenging diseases affecting the ability of the subjects to stand and walk. However, there is not enough evidence regarding subjects' NCLBP gait. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the gait of this group of subjects.

The results of the current study show that the spatiotemporal gait parameters of the NCLBP group were the same as those of the normal group. Moreover, there was no significant difference between the kinematics of the trunk, pelvic, hip, knee, and ankle joints of normal and NCLBP groups. The hip, knee, and ankle movements differed between the groups. This means that the internal extensor moment of hip and knee joints decreased. Moreover, the ankle plantar flexion moment decreased, possibly due to weakness of the ankle plantar flexor due to LBP.

Based on the results of various research studies, those with LBP may have a longer stance duration and shorter step length compared to normal subjects. This is due to a rigid or more careful walking pattern that reduces the pain associated with LBP [10,20]. However, the results of this research contradict the previous findings. Therefore, it can be concluded that NCLBP subjects behave according to the Avoidance-Endurance model (AEM). It means that they ignore their pain and persist in being as active as before despite the pain [21-23].

The other parameters selected in this study were the kinematics of the trunk, pelvic, and leg joints. As can be seen from the results of this research, there was no significant difference between the kinematics of hip joints of the normal and NCLBP subjects. These results support that lumbar and pelvic motion coordination was not more rigid in any planes. This finding supports the idea that pain with musculoskeletal origin in NCLBP patients had no significant influence on the range of motion of the lumbar spine and pelvis in three dimensions. This is the same finding as Vogt et al. [10]. These results are in contrast to Cimolin et al. [24]. However, it should be emphasized that the difference between the results may be due to the type of the participants. In the study done by Cimolin, the effects of obesity and chronic low back pain were evaluated.

The moments of the hip, knee, and ankle joints were also analyzed in this study. As shown in Table 4, the internal extensor moments of the hip, knee, and ankle joints decreased significantly in subjects with NCLBP, which seems to be due to muscle weakness. A decrease in hip joint moment may be due to a change in ground reaction forces applied to the leg (especially during heel strike) or proprioceptive feedback alteration [15,25]. This influences the ability of these subjects during level walking and increases energy consumption [26-28]. Therefore, strengthening this group of muscles is recommended in this group of subjects to improve their abilities during walking.

Some limitations should be acknowledged in this study. Only female subjects were recruited. Although there seems to be no difference between the gait of males and females, conducting the same study with a group of subjects of both genders is recommended. Moreover, the hip, knee, and ankle joint moments were calculated using an inverse dynamic approach (using Visual 3D software). Therefore, it is recommended that the performance of muscles be evaluated using EMG in future studies.

CONCLUSION

The main finding of this study was that individuals with NCLBP experienced a decrease in moments at the hip, knee, and ankle joints, which could be attributed to muscular weakness. This suggests that the ankle plantar flexors and hip and knee extensors in individuals with NCLBP may lack power. Therefore, it is recommended that individuals in this group focus on strengthening the hip and knee extensors as well as the ankle plantar flexors. Additionally, this study's results confirmed no differences in the pelvic, hip, and knee joint kinematics between the NCLBP group and the normal subjects.

Authors Contribution: Conceptualization: M.K, M.H.Z; methodology: M.K; software: M.K; validation: M.B; formal analysis, M.B and M.K; investigation: M.K, M.H.Z; resources: M.H.Z; data curation: M.K; writing—original draft preparation: M.K, M.B; writing—review and editing: H.K, A.S, F.G, and M.A; visualization: M.A; supervision: M.B; project administration: M.B. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: The study protocol received approval from the Ethics Committee of Shiraz University of Medical Sciences (Ethics number: IR.SUMS.REHAB.REC.1399.034)

Acknowledgments: None.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. Koes BW, van Tulder MW, Thomas S. Diagnosis and treatment of low back pain. *BMJ*. 2006;332(7555):1430-1434.
2. Meucci RD, Fassa AG, Faria NM. Prevalence of chronic low back pain: systematic review. *Rev Saude Publica*. 2015;49:1. doi: 10.1590/S0034-8910.2015049005874. Epub 2015 Oct 20.
3. Hoy D, Brooks P, Blyth F, Buchbinder R. The Epidemiology of low back pain. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol*. 2010;24(6):769-781.
4. Koes BW, van Tulder MW, Thomas S. Diagnosis and treatment of low back pain. *BMJ*. 2006 Jun 17;332(7555):1430-1434. doi: 10.1136/bmj.332.7555.1430.
5. Rowe P, White M. Three dimensional, lumbar spinal kinematics during walking, following mild musculo-skeletal low back pain in nurses. *Gait Posture*. 1996;4:242-251.
6. Jo HJ, Song AY, Lee KJ, Lee DC, Kim YH, Sung PS. A kinematic analysis of relative stability of the lower extremities between subjects with and without chronic low back pain. *Eur Spine J*. 2011;20(8):1297-1303.
7. Chockalingam N, Chatterley F, Healy AC, Greenhalgh A, Branthwaite HR. Comparison of pelvic complex kinematics during treadmill and overground walking. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2012;93(12):2302-2308.
8. Lamoth CJ, Beek PJ, Meijer OG. Pelvis-thorax coordination in the transverse plane during gait. *Gait Posture*. 2002;16(2):101-114.
9. Lamoth CJ, Meijer OG, Daffertshofer A, Wuisman PI, Beek PJ. Effects of chronic low back pain on trunk coordination and back muscle activity during walking: changes in motor control. *Eur Spine J*. 2006;15(1):23-40.
10. Vogt L, Pfeifer K, Portscher, Banzer W. Influences of nonspecific low back pain on three-dimensional lumbar spine kinematics in locomotion. *Spine*. 2001;26(17):1910-1919.
11. Huang YP, Bruijn SM, Lin JH, Meijer OG, Wu WH, Abbasi-Bafghi H, et al. Gait adaptations in low back pain patients with lumbar disc herniation: trunk coordination and arm swing. *Eur Spine J*. 2011 Mar;20(3):491-499. doi: 10.1007/s00586-010-1639-8. Epub 2010 Dec 24.
12. Papi E, Bull AMJ, McGregor AH. Is there evidence to use kinematic/kinetic measures clinically in low back pain patients? A systematic review. *Clin Biomech (Bristol, Avon)*. 2018 Jun;55:53-64. doi: 10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2018.04.006. Epub 2018 Apr 11.
13. Vogt L, Pfeifer K, Banzer W. Neuromuscular control of walking with chronic low-back pain. *Man Ther*. 2003 Feb;8(1):21-28. doi: 10.1054/math.2002.0476.
14. MacRae CS, Critchley D, Lewis JS, Shortland A. Comparison of standing postural control and gait parameters in people with and without chronic low back pain: a cross-sectional case-control study. *BMJ Open Sport Exerc Med*. 2018 Jan 23;4(1):e000286. doi: 10.1136/bmjsem-2017-000286.
15. Lee CE, Simmonds MJ, Etnyre BR, Morris GS. Influence of pain distribution on gait characteristics in patients with low back pain: part 1: vertical ground reaction force. *Spine*. 2007;32(12):1329-1336.

16. Mazzocchio R, Scarfò GB, Mariottini A, Muzii VF, Palma L. Recruitment curve of the soleus H-reflex in chronic back pain and lumbosacral radiculopathy. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord*. 2001;2:4-4.
17. Esrafilian A, Karimi MT, Amiri P, Fatoye F. Performance of subjects with knee osteoarthritis during walking: differential parameters. *Rheumatol Int*. 2013.
18. Amin S, Luepingsak N, McGibbon CA, LaValley MP, Krebs DE, Felson DT. Knee adduction moment and development of chronic knee pain in elders. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2004;51(3):371-376.
19. Eng JI, Winter DA. Kinetic analysis of the lower limbs during walking: what information can be gained from a three-dimensional model? *J Biomech*. 1995;28(0021-9290 (Print)):753-758.
20. Keefe FJ, Hill RW. An objective approach to quantifying pain behavior and gait patterns in low back pain patients. *Pain*. 1985;21(2):153-161.
21. Papi E, Bull AM, McGregor AH. Is there evidence to use kinematic/kinetic measures clinically in low back pain patients? A systematic review. *Clinical Biomechanics*. 2018 Jun 1;55:53-64. doi: 10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2018.04.006.
22. Krekoukias G, Sakellari V, Anastasiadi E, Gioftos G, Dimitriadis Z, Soultanis K, et al. Gait kinetic and kinematic changes in chronic low back pain patients and the effect of manual therapy: a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Med*. 2021 Aug 15;10(16):3593. doi: 10.3390/jcm10163593.
23. Bidari S, Ghorbani F, Barati K, Jalaeddini A, Pourahmadi M. The Role of Non-rigid Pelvic Belts in Managing Pregnancy-related Pelvic Girdle Pain and Low Back Pain: A Systematic Review. *Iran Rehabil J*. 2024;22(2):151-166.
24. Cimolin V, Vismara L, Galli M, Zaina F, Negrini S, Capodaglio P. Effects of obesity and chronic low back pain on gait. *J Neuroeng Rehabil*. 2011;8:55.
25. Tong MH, Mousavi SJ, Kiers H, Ferreira P, Refshauge K, van Dieën J. Is there a relationship between lumbar proprioception and low back pain? A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2017 Jan 1;98(1):120-136. doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2016.05.016.
26. Lin J, Halaki M, Rajan P, Leaver A. Relationship between proprioception and pain and disability in people with non-specific low back pain: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Spine*. 2019 May 15;44(10):E606-E617. doi: 10.1097/BRS.0000000000002917.
27. Carvalho AR, Ribeiro Bertor WR, Briani RV, Zanini GM, Silva LI, Andrade A, et al. Effect of nonspecific chronic low back pain on walking economy: an observational study. *J Mot Behav*. 2016 May 3;48(3):218-226. doi: 10.1080/00222895.2015.1079162.
28. Henchoz Y, Soldini N, Peyrot N, Malatesta D. Energetics and mechanics of walking in patients with chronic low back pain and healthy matched controls. *Eur J Appl Physiol*. 2015 Nov;115:2433-2443. doi: 10.1007/s00421-015-3227-4.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative

Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).